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SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN THE ERA OF CONNECTIVISM: A VIEW FROM CHIAVENATO AND SIEMENS

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the application of Chiavenato and Siemens management theories in the contemporary school context, considering the influence of digital connectivity. It seeks to understand how school management can adapt and use connectivity effectively to improve the educational environment and student development. Using qualitative methodology, with a literature review and conceptual analysis, it examines the relationship between school management and connectivity. The conclusions highlight the importance of adapting school management practices to take advantage of the opportunities offered by connectivity, while facing the challenges of this reality, aiming to ensure an educational environment that meets the demands of the digital society. The study highlights the need for efficient integration of connectivity to promote an educational environment aligned with the demands of an increasingly digital society.

KEYWORDS: Connectivity. School Management. Chiavenato and Siemens Theories